

Measurement of Sovereign Bond's Sensitivity and Application of Convexity Model

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Abstract : Purpose- *The study aims to investigate the impact of convexity on sovereign bond (G-Sec) by analyzing sensitivity of price to change in yield with varying maturity period. Due to the sensitive volatility during the crisis period, investors had to adjust their investment strategies in light of difficult preconditions. The crisis era is noteworthy not because it was a financial crisis but rather because of the large yield revisions it brought about. These circumstances implied higher earnings associated with increased exposure to convexity. This research work will be beneficial for the investors who are seeing changes in market yields on sovereign bond may take the advantage of this convex methodology.*

Design/Methodology - *The present study is based on sovereign bond and it employs convexity model which is a key factor in this assessment of sovereign bond's sensitivity. The various maturity period of sovereign bond (G-Sec) series from 2024 to 2073 were taken into consideration for this empirical analysis. The study also uses regression and correlations to illuminate the relations among variables.*

Findings - *The findings of this study indicates that the prices move more in response to changes in yields when the convexity measure is higher. Bond that has a highest maturity level has a larger convexity and a higher price sensitivity. Thus, it can be said that price sensitivity increases with duration.*

Originality - *This study is one of the few research published till date which will add substantial values in sovereign bond and ought to significantly advance the concept of previously available models.*

Keywords : Sovereign Bond, Price, Yields, Price, Convexity, Duration, Sensitivity.

Introduction

For government bonds, investors are often protected from default risk of any kind because central government bond specially enjoy sovereign guarantee. In the study of (Karmakar, 2023) opined that G-Sec are referred to as risk-free gilt-edged instruments because they essentially have no default risk. The study of (Blanco, 2001) emphasizes the significance of the government bond which is distinguished from other securities by their low default risk, great liquidity in the market with variety of maturities. One of the fundamental principles of sovereignty which distinct government bond from other bonds (Eaton & Gersovitz, 1981) (Panizza, Sturzenegger, & Zettelmeyer, 2009). The outcome of the lack of a bankruptcy procedure and a supranational legal body that might force creditors to pay them back. As a result, numerous theoretical works have explored different justifications for the existence of government bond (Aguiar & Amador, 2013). Furthermore, research continues to examine legislative and prescribed procedures to enhance sovereign bond performance and bring them more akin to a corporate bond standards (Krueger, 2002)(IMF, 2013). According to (Krishnamurthy & Jorgensen, 2012) government bonds are taken as collateral since they are usually safe and liquid.

As a result, in order to raise money for public expenditure and a variety of needs, including operating costs, debt repayment, interest payments on existing debt, and other essential government spending, governments are issuing sovereign bonds. Sovereign bonds constitute a substantial source of funding for governments, in addition to tax revenue. It might, however, be a trade-off between risk and return, depending on the country's health that issued it and its financial situation. Meanwhile, an empirical literature has revealed over time the distinct characteristics of governmental bonds and its default (Mitchener & Trebesch, 2023). For a number of reasons, sovereign bond offers an insightful prism through which to examine political risk (Tomz & Wright, 2009). The Government of India recently announced for securities that will be repurchased at auction for a total of Rs 60,000 crore (RBI, 2024). The reason behind is to use this excess to pay off some of its debt ahead of time in an effort to reduce future repayment constraints and manage its debt load proactively. In tandem, this boosts investor trust on sovereign bonds. Repurchases have the potential to lower interest costs for the government by increasing demand for bonds, which in turn lowers rates. In the preceding fiscal year, the Indian government borrowed a record amount from the market, but for the first time in nearly two decades, there was no devolution on primary dealers for sovereign bonds. Investors in fixed income will be focusing on the government's commitment to budgetary

consolidation. Over the next couple of years, India's G-Sec market may see inflows of up to hundred billion dollar once-functioning issues are resolved, causing significant institutional investors to choose debt in the world's fastest-growing major economy, including sovereign wealth funds and central bank reserve. Banks have made significant gains through interest and trading income on government bonds in recent years due to rate cuts.

Banks and Insurance companies are the largest investors in sovereign bond and at the time of market uncertainties taking the opportunities to produce profit from changes in yields or balance low interest revenue through trading income (Acharya & Steffen, 2015), (Andreeva & Vlassopoulos, 2019), (Molyneux, Reghezza, Torriero, & Williams, 2021). Furthermore, (Kim, Kim, & Ryan, 2019) and (Beatty, Chamberlain, & Magliolo, 1995) find that in order to mitigate the effect on banks' capital, banks may decrease the average maturity period. The world financial crisis that began in 2008 was the cause of the worst recession which had a negative impact on many different types of businesses and industries. The world's financial markets were shook by Lehman Brothers' collapse. The bond risk premium abruptly increased to five percent from its usual range of zero. (McKibbin & Stoeckel, 2009). However, because interest rates have dropped to their lowest points in history, the banking system's holdings of government bonds are risky (Sy, 2005) as because majority of the government bonds held by banks and other financial institutions are long-term fixed-rate bonds. For this reason, understanding the convexity model is crucial for making investment decisions. Convexity adjustments can be fairly considerable when the value of a security may be dispersed over a wider range of values and there is a longer maturity period (Burgess, 2019). Hence one can more effectively manage bond investments and calculate the effect of various yield components on bond prices if comprehend the ideas of approximation modified duration and convexity adjustment. It is a tool for risk management as well as a gauge of how susceptible bond values are to changes in interest rates. When computing price changes based on duration, the yield variations might be taken into consideration. This is due to the non-linear relationship between bond price and yield. Researchers and professionals still frequently allude to the parallel shift of the interest rate curve even if it is an unlikely theory (Lajili & Rakotondratsimba, 2012).

Convexity shape also provide information about the yield curve's behaviour. Compared to low convex yield curves, which are flatter, high convexity yield curves are frequently steeper. By comprehending the convexity of the yield curve, investors can predict future changes in interest rates and adjust their investment

strategies. Duration and convexity have multiple applications, ranging from financial institution credit pipeline hedging to future liability immunization. It is a crucial instrument for determining and controlling interest rate risk exposure. Compared to bonds with equal risk associated with interest rate, as signposted by modified duration, the more convex bond will offer less downside and more upside in the event that rates rise.

Figure-1- Convexity of a Benchmark Bond (G-Sec)

Unfortunately, there are limits to the duration's utility as a gauge in sensitivity of interest rate. Although the statistic computes a bond yields and price movements have a linear connection, but in practice the price and yield movements that have a convex connection. The above graph of G-Sec benchmark bond illustrates how prices would change in response to a change in yields with a curved line.

Convexity is a metric used to quantify how changes in interest rates affect the price of bonds. The price of the bond increases with a decrease in the yield and decreases with an increase in the yield. This pricing phenomena that happens when changes in upstream prices cause downstream prices to respond

differently, depending on the features of price and yield relationship may be seen in Figure 1 as a convexity curve. When there is an advantageous shift in yields, or a decrease in yield, convexity causes the bond price to climb more than it would when there is an unfavourable shift in yields, or an increase in yield, of the same amount. Convexity adjustment is a technique used to enhance estimates of how bond prices fluctuate in response to changes in interest rates, more on the upward than the downward side; convexity decreases when higher yields cause the price-yield curve to flatten.

The duration is actually longer with lower yields, so when rates decline, investors may book profit from enhanced rate sensitivity. On the other hand, duration shortens as yields rise, which again benefits investors by reducing the price effect of rising rates. When a bond is positively convex, prices are increasing more quickly than they are decreasing more slowly in addition to being higher than the linear approximation. Therefore, bond prices rise more quickly than they fall (Schrier, 2023). Therefore, convexity is more beneficial on the upside than the downside for the same reason. Based on empirical results on convexity, this paper investigates the degree to which sovereign bond prices with different maturities are sensitive to fluctuations in interest rates by using as accurate as the convexity-augmented formula and to provide suggestions and important didactic advantages and much more computationally efficient based on empirical results of convexity.

Literature Survey

Interest rate fluctuations and inflation are the primary elements that affect the risk of investing in government bonds (Muharam, 2013) (Yusuf & Prasetyo, 2019). The maturity and interest rate risk are the factors for pricing bond (Livingston & Zhou, 2005), (Knowles & Su, 2005), (Ajilouni, 2012). In terms of its analysis, sensitivity analysis is the standard method of risk evaluation used to assess the risk associated with government bonds and this introduces the idea of duration, which is a measure of the security value's to its rates (Jorion, 2007). In order to improve the approximation of bond pricing, (Fisher & Weil, 1971) established convexity as Modified Duration might be imprecise for significant interest rate fluctuations. Convexity is an interest rate-to-bond price derivative (Bodie, Kane, & Marcus, 2008). It is a well-established which represent the bond's yield and duration, as well as its convexity, can be used to calculate the bond's relative value and gauge its risk acquaintance (Christensen & Sorensen, 1994), (Chance & Jordan, 1996). Duration shows how the bond price responds to each percentile change of yield. Duration is a useful indicator of how sensitive bond prices are

to fluctuations in interest rates (Xu, 2020). Through multiple numerical examples, (Shirvani & Wilbratte, 2005) demonstrated that the convexity-augmented Macaulay formula produces more accurate coupon bond price volatility estimates. Sensitivity analysis with the help of duration with convexity has been made studied by (Maruddani & Hoyyi, 2017) and shown to have a lower error value than alternative techniques.

Published simultaneously (Flesaker, 1993) who developed a convexity adjustment for calculating the predicted Libor rate in a continuous and discrete scenario and (Ritchken & Sankarasubramanian, 1993) who discovered a convexity formula for averaging contracts, were the significant references on the convexity adjustment. A lot of progress was made in the years that followed. Later efforts by (Benhamou, 2000) and (Hagan, 2003) expand the convexity adjustment to a wider range of payoffs. Alternatively, by employing other tactics and methodology to measure the volatility changes studied by (Pelsser, 2001).

Objectives of the Study

1. To assess the association between price and yields of G-Sec.
2. To determine the sensitivity of the bond's price to change in yield of Government Bonds with varying maturity period series.
3. To provide suitable measures on risk management for future endeavors.

Methodology :

The research paper relies on secondary data that was collected from the published report of Clearing Corporation of India Ltd with varying maturity periods of sovereign bonds (popularly known as G-Sec) from 2024 to 2073. The Convexity Model as developed by (Macaulay, 1938) has been used in this paper to show the volatility of price to change in yield of sovereign Bonds with varying maturity period series. The results are analyzed by using statistical tools viz; Regression, Correlation etc. Further results is compared based on these methods to determine the development of sovereign bonds. Bond's price is determined by several elements, the most significant of which is the YTM, or actualized interest rates. This is evident since the present value of a bond's projected future cash flows determines its value. The cash flows of a coupon-paying bond are known in advance, but the bond's current value must be calculated by the investor taking the discounting rate into consideration.

$$\text{Bond Price (P)} = \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{c_1}{y^1} + \frac{c_2}{y^2} + \frac{c_t}{y^t} \dots \dots \dots \quad (\text{Fabozzi, 1999})$$

----- equation (i)

Where,

C = Coupon, n = number of cash flows, F = face value, Y = yield to maturity, t = term to maturity.

The yield that guarantees that the present value of future cash flows equals the purchase price, providing the bond is held to maturity. It is the current rate of return if coupons are reinvested at the current yield until the bond expires. As a result, the denominator of the bond pricing function is what the YTM and interest rate relate to. Bond yields are calculated by dividing the bond's annual coupon rate by its current market value. The yield is given in percentage form.

$$\text{Yield to Maturity (YTM)} = \frac{C + \frac{F - P}{t}}{\frac{F + P}{2}} \quad (\text{Purnomo, Wijaya, \& Pratama, 2022})$$

----- equation (ii)

Where,

C = coupon, F= face value, P = price, t = term to maturity.

Duration is essentially a measure of risk associated with interest rates on bond prices. Duration measures the bond's price sensitivity to a 100 basis point change in interest rates (Fabozzi, 1999). Because a larger portion of their future cash flows will be discounted at the new rate, bonds with longer durations are more vulnerable to interest rate risk. Frederick Macaulay first proposed the concept; his Macaulay duration is shown as follows :

$$\text{Duration (D)} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^n \frac{t \times Ct}{(1+y)^2}}{\sum_{t=1}^n \frac{Ct}{(1+y)^t}} \quad (\text{Zhang, 2022}) \quad \text{-----equation (iii)}$$

Where,

C = Coupon, n = number of cash flows, t = term to maturity and y = yield to maturity.

The most suitable duration metric for option-free bullet bonds is Modified duration, on which our analysis is based. It is computed by taking the yield plus one plus the Macaulay duration.

$$\text{Modified Duration (MD)} = \frac{\text{Duration}}{1 + \frac{\text{Yield}}{2}} \quad (\text{CCIL, 2012}) \quad \text{-----equation (iv)}$$

Convexity is a measurement of the price of the securities movements' in relation to fluctuation of interest rates based on duration changes (Macaulay, 1938). Similar to duration, convexity provides information on how the price of a bond is impacted by the changes of rate of interest. Side by side interest rate sensitivity's second order criterion is represented by the non-linear character of the price-yield relationship. For this reason, convexity is a longer measure than time. Whether rates rise or fall, the duration-measured price shift is assumed to have the same impact on prices. The fact that the price gain for a given yield shift is really greater than the price decline is a crucial characteristic of bond values.

$$\text{Convexity (C)} = \frac{(V -)(V +) - 2P_0}{P_0 \times (0.01)^2} \quad (\text{CCIL, 2012}) \quad \text{----- equation (v)}$$

Where, P_0 denotes the current price before change any yield. The bond prices determined by adding or subtracting 100 bps to the YTM are represented by $V+$ and $V-$.

Therefore the changes in price due to Convexity for 100 bps is the variance between holding bond price and effective bond price due to convexity.

The convex relationship explains a rise in the required yield results in a different percentage price change than a fall in the required yield. When evaluating price sensitivity for bigger, non-linear fluctuations in interest rates, convexity is more useful since it takes into account the bond's price-yield relationship.

Hypothesis :

H_{01} : There is no significant association between price and yield with convexity.

H_{A1} : There is significant association between price and yield with convexity.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the sensitivity of price if there is a 100 bps change in the yield.

H_{A2}: There is a significant difference in the sensitivity of price if there is a 100 bps change in the yield.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Here assessed the risk associated on interest rate with the portfolio of sovereign bond using the duration/convexity method. This method uses the bond price-yield connection to estimate how bond prices will fluctuate in response to changes in yields. A bond's volatility increases due to change in rate of interest with its maturity period. Bond prices and yields have a convex price-yield connection, hence small yield variations are also taken into consideration using a convexity metric. Duration calculates the expected change in the bond price in response to changes in rate of interest. It discounts all cash flows to their present value, taking into account principle and interest payments as well. When a bond has a lower coupon, its duration is longer; when a bond has no coupon, its duration is equal to its maturity. Bond duration, which is a measure of risk associated with interest rate, is used to calculate the average bond maturity time. Duration is a measure of how sensitive bond prices or bond range prices are to changes in interest rates. Two factors influence bond price fluctuations in reaction to changes in interest rates: the changed duration and convexity of the bond. The proportional importance of these factors depends on the magnitude of the interest rate shift as well as the bond's maturity and coupon rate. While duration may be a reasonable estimate of the potential price impact of small changes in rates, it may not be as helpful for assessing the long-term effects of major changes in interest rates. This is due to the convex rather than linear connection between bond yields and bond prices. The most accurate measure of a bond's interest rate sensitivity is the product of convexity yields and modified duration. However, it should be noted that the assumption that the yield curves are parallel serves as the foundation for the approximation of bond price changes caused by changes in rate of interest. Convexity quantifies the price fluctuation of a bond that is not covered by duration. It is known as the bond's price's second derivative with respect to interest rates; the first derivative is duration. Therefore, convexity measures the curvature of the bond price-yield relationship and shows how a bond's duration changes with changes in rate of interest.

Table-1 : Sensitivity Analysis through the Convexity Model

Sl. No.	Name of the Security	Coupon Rate	Bond Price	YTM	Duration	Mduration	V+	V-	Convexity	Price due to increase in yield by 100 bps	Price due to decrease in yield by 100 bps	Price Variation
1	9.15% GS 2024	9.15%	101.25	7.03%	0.60	0.58	100.65	101.85	0.64	100.65	101.85	1.20
2	5.15% GS 2025	5.15%	97.09	7.09%	1.53	1.48	95.65	98.57	3.03	95.65	98.57	2.92
3	8.15% G S 2026	8.15%	102.50	7.09%	2.37	2.29	100.12	104.95	6.94	100.12	104.95	4.83
4	8.28% GS 2027	8.28%	103.57	7.10%	3.09	2.98	100.53	106.72	11.02	100.53	106.72	6.20
5	7.25% GS 2028	7.25%	100.59	7.09%	3.90	3.77	96.79	104.58	18.18	96.79	104.58	7.79
6	6.79% GS 2029	6.79%	98.66	7.08%	4.75	4.59	94.18	103.40	26.49	94.18	103.40	9.23
7	8.97% GS 2030	8.97%	109.79	7.10%	5.11	4.94	104.40	115.53	32.11	104.40	115.53	11.13
8	6.68% GS 2031	6.68%	97.72	7.08%	5.96	5.76	92.27	103.57	40.99	92.27	103.57	11.29
9	8.33% GS 2032	8.33%	107.97	7.06%	6.32	6.11	101.61	114.85	47.61	101.61	114.85	13.23
10	7.24% GS 2033	7.24%	101.23	7.06%	7.00	6.76	94.54	108.54	60.72	94.54	108.54	14.00
11	7.73% GS 2034	7.73%	104.75	7.09%	7.41	7.15	97.46	112.78	69.31	97.46	112.78	15.32
12	6.67% GS 2035	6.67%	96.55	7.11%	8.08	7.80	89.25	104.64	82.23	89.25	104.64	15.39
13	7.41% GS 2036	7.41%	102.54	7.10%	8.34	8.05	94.56	111.44	89.86	94.56	111.44	16.89
14	7.18% GS 2037	7.18%	100.78	7.09%	8.69	8.40	92.67	109.86	96.86	92.67	109.86	17.19
15	7.62% GS 2039	7.62%	104.85	7.10%	9.46	9.13	95.83	115.10	116.36	95.83	115.10	19.27
16	8.30% GS 2040	8.30%	111.46	7.10%	9.41	9.09	101.78	122.49	120.90	101.78	122.49	20.70
17	8.83% GS 2041	8.83%	117.29	7.10%	9.68	9.35	106.81	129.32	131.98	106.81	129.32	22.51
18	8.30% GS 2042	8.30%	112.10	7.12%	10.12	9.77	101.71	124.11	144.27	101.71	124.11	22.41
19	9.23% GS 2043	9.23%	122.40	7.10%	10.15	9.80	111.01	135.60	148.40	111.01	135.60	24.59
20	8.17% GS 2044	8.17%	111.38	7.11%	10.57	10.21	100.58	123.98	162.72	100.58	123.98	23.40
21	8.13% GS 2045	8.13%	110.97	7.12%	10.75	10.38	100.09	123.71	167.89	100.09	123.71	23.61
22	7.06% GS 2046	7.06%	99.47	7.11%	11.19	10.80	89.24	111.57	187.89	89.24	111.57	22.34
23	7.72% GS 2049	7.72%	107.20	7.10%	11.64	11.24	95.91	120.69	205.55	95.91	120.69	24.77
24	6.67% GS 2050	6.67%	94.65	7.12%	12.20	11.79	84.26	107.18	227.59	84.26	107.18	22.92
25	6.99% GS 2051	6.99%	98.50	7.11%	12.25	11.83	87.67	111.62	232.18	87.67	111.62	23.96
26	7.36% GS 2052	7.36%	103.06	7.11%	12.45	12.02	91.74	116.80	234.27	91.74	116.80	25.07
27	7.30% GS 2053	7.30%	102.26	7.11%	12.37	11.94	90.93	116.05	240.41	90.93	116.05	25.11
28	7.37% GS 2054	7.37%	103.16	7.11%	12.51	12.08	91.69	117.14	244.08	91.69	117.14	25.46
29	7.72% GS 2055	7.72%	107.53	7.12%	12.41	11.98	95.49	122.28	252.71	95.49	122.28	26.79
30	7.63% GS 2059	7.63%	106.36	7.13%	12.90	12.46	94.17	121.49	275.89	94.17	121.49	27.32
31	6.80% GS 2060	6.80%	95.67	7.13%	13.23	12.77	84.47	109.68	293.06	84.47	109.68	25.21
32	6.95% GS 2061	6.95%	97.86	7.11%	13.29	12.83	86.36	112.27	297.62	86.36	112.27	25.90
33	7.40% GS 2062	7.40%	103.56	7.13%	13.45	12.99	91.46	118.72	296.13	91.46	118.72	27.26
34	7.25% GS 2063	7.25%	101.54	7.13%	13.28	12.82	89.62	116.51	301.13	89.62	116.51	26.90
35	7.46% GS 2073	7.46%	104.75	7.11%	13.67	13.20	92.12	120.95	341.81	92.12	120.95	28.83

Source : Authors' computation.

It is evident from the above Table-1 that the prices move more in response to changes in yields when the convexity measure is higher which is shown as a positive number. The bond that will mature in 2073 has a larger convexity and a higher price sensitivity of 341.81. Thus, it can be said that price sensitivity increases with duration. In a similar vein, the security that matures in 2024 has an extremely low convexity of 0.64. This indicates that the price sensitivity is lower for shorter security durations. Therefore, investors can learn more about the possible risk and return profiles of fixed income instruments by examining convexity. Similar result also been found in the study of (Aoun, Viard, & Marquer, 2021) that convexity is the driving force behind long-term bonds.

Table-2 : Regression Analysis

Analysis	SoS	df	MS	F	Sig.
Regression	206023.874	2	103011.937	19.868	.000 ^a
Residual	165917.258	32	5184.914		
Total	371941.132	34			
a. Predictors: (Constant), YTM, Bond Price					
b. Dependent Variable: Convexity					

(Ozili, 2023) in his study states that R-square values between should lies between 0.50 and 0.99 in social science study, especially when the majority of the explanatory factors are statistically significant. The aforementioned analysis of R² values (0.554) shows a significant impact on the dependent variable. It is evident from the regression analysis that the Price and Yield have impact on convexity measurement. Since $F_{\text{calculated}} > F_{\text{tabulated}}$, with significant at the 0.01 level established the same. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a significant association between price and yield with convexity.

Table-3 : Correlations Analysis

Analysis		Convexity	Price Variation
Convexity	Pearson-Correlation	1	.924**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	35	35
Price Variation	Pearson-Correlation	.924**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	35	35
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

The bond maturing in 2024 has a price variation of 1.20, while the bond maturing in 2073 has a price variation of 28.83. Table-2 indicates that the price variation increases as the maturity increases. Table-3 clearly illustrates the positive correlation between convexity and price variations. It is evident from the correlation analysis that the convexity and price variation have a positive relation and increasing with the increase in maturity period. Since $F_{\text{calculated}} > F_{\text{tabulated}}$, with significant at the 0.01 level established the same. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in the sensitivity of price if there is a 100 bps change in the yield.

Conclusions

The convexity is arbitrage-free priced over longer time frames, which can produce excess returns during aberrant volatility periods. Therefore, using convexity as a tool to take advantage of volatility expectations that are higher than the market average may be beneficial in the longer period of time. A bond with higher convexity will provide less downside in the event that rates rise and more upside in the event that they fall. Bonds with lower coupons are more convex for the same maturity and yield.

Longer duration bond have largest risk and volatility. Only convexity can estimate the variability on longer duration bonds which typically exhibit greater volatile and susceptible to changes in interest rates. However, for modest rate changes duration alone is merely a reliable indicator of price changes. Convexity is required to account for the change in price that duration does not for greater or longer changes in rates. Bonds with higher convexity will yield higher income if the drop in rates of interest is anticipated. Similarly, the loss brought on by unanticipated. A higher convexity bond results in a smaller interest rate increase. Therefore, it makes no difference if interest rates rise or fall; convexity still improves the portfolio's performance. Consequently, the portfolio's convexity ought to be increased if higher interest rate volatility is anticipated.

Finally, sovereign bonds (G-Sec) can be a wise choice for those seeking low-risk investment approach to create a stable and trading income. Interest income can provide steady revenue, and the convexity model can guarantee trading income.

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